

THE SMARANDACHE COMPLEX

The Smarandache Complex (with the accent on the first syllable): is a collection of fears stemming from previous unsuccessful experience or from unconscious feelings that, wanting to do something <S>, the result would be <Anti-S>, which give rise to feelings, attitudes, and ideas pushing the subject towards a deviation of action <S> eventually towards an <Anti-S> action. (From the positive and negative brain's electrical activities.)

For example: A shy boy, attempting to invite a girl to dance, inhabits himself of fear she would turn him down...

How to manage this phobia? To dote and anti-dote!
By transforming it into an opposite one, thinking differently, and being fear in our mind that we would pass our expectancies but we shouldn't.

Psychodrama could be a treatment way.

Reference:

Smarandache, Florentin, "Neutrosophy. / Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic", American Research Press, Rehoboth, 1989.